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First records of *Paracymus aeneus* (GERMAR, 1823) and *Enochrus segmentinotatus* (KUWERT, 1888) (Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae) from the Cabo Verde Archipelago and confirmation of the occurrence of *Ochthebius hesperides* BALFOUR-BROWNE, 1976 (Hydraenidae) on Sal Island

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Abstract: *Paracymus aeneus* (GERMAR, 1823) and *Enochrus segmentinotatus* (KUWERT, 1888) are recorded for the first time from Sal Island in the Cabo Verde Archipelago. The presence of *Ochthebius hesperides* BALFOUR-BROWNE, 1976 (Hydraenidae), previously regarded as extinct, is also confirmed. The results indicate that the water beetle fauna of Sal Island is species-poor, which is consistent with earlier observations on the biodiversity of the Cape Verde Islands. At the same time, the discovery of new and rediscovered taxa highlights the insufficient state of entomological exploration of the archipelago.

Key words: Cabo Verde, Macaronesia, new faunistic records, Hydrophilidae, Hydraenidae.

INTRODUCTION

The Cabo Verde Islands are located in the central Atlantic Ocean, about 620 km west of the African coast, at the latitude of Cape Verde. The archipelago comprises ten main islands and five smaller islets. Sal belongs to the Windward Islands and covers an area of 216 km². It is a low, largely sandy island with a predominantly desert landscape; its highest point is Monte Grande (406 m a.s.l.) (DUARTE & ROMEIRAS 2009).

The Cabo Verde Islands are among the world regions where the beetle fauna is still poorly studied. Only 276 beetle species are known from Sal Island, of which six are aquatic beetles: *Eretes sticticus* (LINNAEUS, 1767) and *Hyphydrus maculatus* BABINGTON, 1841

(Dytiscidae), *Ochthebius balfourbrownnei* JÄCH, 1989 and *O. hesperides* BALFOUR-BROWNE, 1976 (Hydraenidae), and *Enochrus wollastoni* (SHARP, 1870) and *Paracymus phalacroides* (WOLLASTON, 1867) (Hydrophilidae) (OROMÍ *et al.* 2005). Both Dytiscidae species are widely distributed on the African continent; *P. phalacroides* occurs in southern Europe, north-western Africa and the Canary Islands (GARCÍA & CASTILLO 2025), whereas the remaining species are considered endemic to the Cabo Verde Islands (AISTLEITNER & JÄCH 2014).

The small number of beetle species known from Sal Island is partly due to the dry, semi-desert climate, characterized by a long dry season and a short rainy season. Mean annual precipitation is low, although sporadic torrential rains occur during the rainy season (July–October). The island lacks permanent watercourses, and high temperatures and strong winds promote rapid evaporation. A characteristic landscape element is the salt pans (salinas), including reservoirs of oceanic origin.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Beetles were collected using hand nets with a diameter of several centimetres, in saline water body (Fig. 1, 2, 3) near dunes and extensive plots where salt used to be extracted. The margins of the reservoirs were covered with low halophytic vegetation.

Species identification was based on both external morphological characters and the male copulatory organs. Voucher specimens are deposited in the authors' collections.

RESULTS

During surveys conducted on 22–24 March 2025 in the vicinity of Santa Maria, three species of aquatic beetles were recorded:

Hydrophilidae

Paracymus aeneus (GERMAR, 1823) (Fig. 4)

Cabo Verde, Sal Island, NE of Santa Maria (16°36'27.2"N 22°53'49.6"W) (Fig. 1), 22.03.2025, 3 exx., leg. Andrzej Lason, Marek Miłkowski; Santa Maria, artificial drying salt pan, (16°35'52"N 22°54'59"W), 23.03.2025, 4 exx., leg. Karol Komosiński;

Enochrus segmentinotatus (KUWERT, 1888) (Fig. 5)

Cabo Verde, Sal Island, NE of Santa Maria (16°36'27.2"N 22°53'49.6"W) (Fig. 1), 22.03.2025, 6 exx. collected and numerous others observed, leg. Andrzej Lason, Marek Miłkowski;

Hydraenidae

Ochthebius hesperides BALFOUR-BROWNE, 1976 (Figs. 6, 7)

Cabo Verde, Sal Island, Santa Maria, artificial drying salt pan (16°35'52"N 22°54'59"W) (Fig. 3), 23.03.2025, 2♀♀ 1♂, leg. Karol Komosiński; Cabo Verde, Sal Island, north of Santa Maria, brackish pool, (16°36'35"N 22°54'53"W), 24.03.2025, 1 ♂, leg. Karol Komosiński.

DISCUSSION

Surveys conducted in March 2025 on Sal Island in the Cabo Verde Archipelago revealed three aquatic beetle species in the Santa Maria area: two new to the archipelago, *Paracymus aeneus* and *Enochrus segmentinotatus*, and a species endemic to Sal Island, *Ochthebius hesperides* (OROMÍ *et al.* 2005).

Paracymus aeneus is a widely distributed Palaearctic species, known from Asia through almost all of Europe and North Africa (FIKÁČEK *et al.* 2015). Likewise, *E. segmentinotatus* occurs in the southern part of the Palaearctic, including North Africa. Their presence on Sal is therefore not surprising, but it had not been documented previously.

Ochthebius hesperides was described from Sal Island in 1976 (JÄCH 1991) and was later regarded as extinct (OROMÍ *et al.* 2005) without providing unequivocal evidence for such an assessment. The present data clearly confirm its current occurrence. Endemism in *O. hesperides* is probably the result of a long-term adaptive process to the island's specific ecological conditions, as well as limited opportunities for inter-island dispersal. It also cannot be excluded that this species inhabits other islands of the archipelago; however, the lack of targeted studies in analogous habitats prevents verification of this hypothesis.

The occurrence of the discussed species in both natural and anthropogenic salinas indicates considerable ecological tolerance. The episodic character of the water bodies, related to short-lived rainfall and rapid desiccation, constitutes an important constraint on the development of aquatic fauna and favours only species adapted to strong fluctuations in environmental conditions.

The results confirm the poverty of the aquatic beetle fauna of Sal Island, consistent with earlier studies (OROMÍ *et al.* 2005, AISTLEITNER & JÄCH 2014). At the same time, documenting two species new to the archipelago and the “rediscovery” of a taxon regarded as extinct demonstrate the very poor state of knowledge of the Cabo Verde entomofauna and indicate an urgent need for further field research.

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Fig. 1. Small saline reservoirs – collecting site of beetles from the family Hydrophilidae (photo M. Miłkowski).

Fig. 2. North of Santa Maria, brackish pool (photo K. Komosiński).

Fig. 3. Santa Maria, artificial drying salt pan (photo K. Komosiński).

Fig. 4. *Paracymus aeneus* (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo A. Lasoń).

Fig. 5. *Enochrus segmentinotatus* (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo A. Lasoń).

Fig. 6. *Ochthebius hesperides* (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo A. Lasoń).

Fig. 7. *Ochthebius hesperides* – aedeagus (scale bar = 0.2 mm) (photo A. Lasoń).

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